

Question Answering using Sentence Similarity, Context Based And Fish Identification from images

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Abstract-- *This research employs a novel algorithm for calculating sentence similarity between brief texts to conduct a thorough analysis of sentence similarity. This is followed by the study's classification of user-inputted questions based on similarity scores, covering a variety of applications including context-based question answering using the RoBERTa-base model tuned on the SQuAD 2.0 dataset, fish recognition from images using Faster R-CNN using MobileNetV3-Large, as well as fish similarity evaluation using k-NN with cosine similarity. A sophisticated knowledge of question semantics is provided by the methodology, which combines advances in NLP, computer vision, as well as similarity metrics. This paves the way for a variety of applications, including contextual inquiry, image-based recognition, and similarity evaluation in relation to fish-related queries.*

Keywords: CNN, cv2, Django, , KNN, Machine Learning, Question-answering, Torch and Transformers

I. INTRODUCTION

The widespread usage of question-answering tools has become essential for enabling smooth communication between humans and computer systems. These tools, which are skilled at responding to user inquiries quickly and accurately, are always changing to satisfy the needs of precise and pertinent information retrieval. Using context-based question-answering strategies to improve accuracy is a major problem in their development.

With the use of cutting-edge models and methods, the research present a novel solution to improve question answering. First, sentences with similarity scores from models such as nlper/gte-large are used to classify question submitted by users. By taking this step, we can more accurately ascertain the nature and context of the investigation.

The research also includes context-based question answering using deepset/roberta-base-squad2 to improve the precision and applicability of answers even more. Its ability to take contextual information into account is excellent, allowing for a more sophisticated comprehension of user queries. Our approach, which differs from typical question-answering models, correctly identifies, and delivers relevant information from the context by leveraging the capabilities of deep learning and natural language processing.

Also demonstrating the project's ability to handle image-based queries in addition to text-based ones. Our implementation of a fish identification module makes use of deep learning techniques to examine user-provided photos.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

[1] For Improving Sentence Representation, Token Attention Sentence-BERT by JAEJIN SEO, SANGWON LEE, LING_LIU AND WONIK CHOI - In this study, TA-SBERT, a ground-breaking sentence embedding model, is introduced, showcasing three unique contributions. To reduce ambiguity in word meaning, the first step in preprocessing entails reducing words to their basic form and removing apostrophes. Second, the TA method improves the model's attention mechanism by dynamically assigning weights to significant words in a sentence. Third, by preventing catastrophic forgetting, the proposed reconstruction loss ensures stability during fine-tuning. The effectiveness of TA-SBERT has been evaluated experimentally on Semantic Textual Similarity (STS) as well as classification tasks using seven datasets. Notably, TA-SBERT outperforms SBERT in STS tasks by an average of 2.04 percent and 1.86 percent for Pearson's and Spearman's rank correlation coefficients, respectively. The SentEval toolkit's classification tasks show an average accuracy improvement of 0.53% with TA-SBERT.

[2] Sentence Similarity Based on Contexts by Xiaofei Sun, Yuxian Meng, Xiang Ao, Fei Wu, Tianwei Zhang, Jiwei Li, and Chun Fan- This ground-breaking work uses the idea that the probabilities for creating similar sentences via a common context should show similarity to introduce a novel framework for measuring sentence similarity. The suggested method uses a pipelined system and starts by collecting a sizable dataset of pairs of sentences with connected similarity scores. To speed up the inference procedure, a surrogate model is subsequently developed with these consequently labeled sentence pairs. The methodology aims to increase assessment of sentence similarity's effectiveness. The efficiency of this framework is proven through extensive experiments, outperforming the performance of current techniques based on sentence embeddings.

[3] Question Difficulty Estimation Based on Attention Model for Question Answering" by Su-Hwan Yoon, Hyun-Je Song, and Seong-Bae Park . Their work focuses on estimating the degree of difficulty of given questions in task-

based question-answering. To deal with question difficulty estimation, the suggested model uses an attention mechanism. By enabling the model to concentrate on pertinent portions of the input sequence, attention models perform an essential part in natural language processing as well as machine learning. In this situation, the attention-based approach seeks to improve comprehension of a variety of questions, ultimately resulting in improved question-answering systems. This study offers insights into using models of attention to estimate question difficulty, a crucial step in improving the effectiveness of question-answering systems.

III. MOTIVATION

This research was inspired by the desire to meet the various informational needs of users who are interested in fish. By providing accurate and pertinent answers, the use of a novel algorithm for determining similarities between sentences in the evaluation of user-inputted query shows a commitment to improving the user experience. The paper aims to provide a thorough understanding of fish-related inquiries through classification of query based on similarity scores and application of advanced methods such as context-based question answering via the RoBERTa-base model as well as fish recognition from images via Faster R-CNN with MobileNetV3-Large. This speeds up information retrieval and guarantees that users get answers to their queries that are appropriate for their context.

The motivation also encompasses a wider range of user engagement with fish-related content. The development of a flexible tool is made possible by the incorporation of advanced understanding of question semantics, drawing from developments in natural language processing, image processing, and similarity metrics. Applications for this tool include contextual analysis, image-based recognition, as well as similarity testing. The seminar paper's ultimate goal is to empower users looking for information about fish by giving them a comprehensive and technologically sophisticated strategy for accessing accurate and pertinent content associated to their query.

IV. METHODOLOGY

In this section, we go over the systematic approach used to develop the Django-based Web Application. The entire process is described below, covering everything from data collection and preprocessing to model integration and user interaction:

A. User Input Evaluation:

The proposed methodology uses an instance of a General Text Embeddings (GTE) model to methodically evaluate the resemblance for user-inputted question in comparison to a predetermined collection of reference sentences during the initial phase of user input evaluation. This GTE model's goal is to identify and determine the semantic connections between textual components, enabling a complex comparison of similarity. As a quantitative indicator of how closely the user-inputted question adhere to

the reference sentences, the output of this evaluation process will produce similarity scores for the user-inputted question. The user-inputted questions can be divided into various contexts as a result of this similarity examination, including context-based question answering, fish recognition from images or similar fishes recognition.

```
Similarity between 'similar fish' and 'Identify the fishes from photo': 87.95671081542969
Similarity between 'fish akin' and 'Identify the fishes from photo': 80.67870330810547
Similarity between 'fish not similar' and 'Identify the fishes from photo': 86.62495422363281
Similarity between 'Identify the fishes' and 'Identify the fishes from photo': 95.55315399169922
```

B. Context-Based Question Answering:

The Roberta-base model and the SQuAD2.0 dataset are both used in the context-based question-answering stage of the methodology. This combination enables the system to accurately understand textual context and respond to user queries. The model's parameters are fine-tuned to better match the task's peculiarities in order to improve performance. This method makes sure the model fits the dataset provided to the best of its ability, increasing accuracy and relevance when producing answers to user questions. The combination of a state-of-the-art model, pertinent dataset, and fine-tuning mechanisms creates a strong foundation for the question-answering model's later stages, ensuring accurate and contextually appropriate answers.

C. Fish Recognition from Images:

To achieve fish recognition from images, the proposed methodology involves the implementation of Faster R-CNN with MobileNetV3-Large, a powerful combination for accurate object detection. The following steps outline the process:

1. **Model Selection:**
Select Faster R-CNN with MobileNetV3-Large as the object detection architecture for fish recognition if you're looking for a balanced combination of accuracy and efficiency.
2. **Dataset Preparation:**
Create a diverse dataset of fish images that fully represents all fish species to enable effective training.
3. **Model Training:**
Start the training process using the meticulously prepared fish image dataset and implement the Faster R-CNN model. Adjust the model's hyperparameters for optimum performance to fine-tune its response to particular fish recognition details.
4. **Data Augmentation:**
During training, use data augmentation techniques, including techniques like rotation and flipping, to improve the model's capacity to deal with variations in fish images.
5. **Validation and Testing:**
Test the model rigorously, evaluating important metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score to determine how well it performs in fish detection.

D. Similar Fishes Recognition:

A k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm utilizing cosine similarity will be implemented for questions pertaining to comparing the similarity of inputted fish. Users can gain knowledge about the similarity between various fish specimens using this method, which makes use of the inherent characteristics of fish to determine their similarity.

E. Integration within Django Framework:

The entire system will be implemented within the Django framework to enhance user interaction. This web framework will make it simple for users to ask questions, get responses, and communicate with the image recognition components.

F. Future Works:

This research aims to broaden its scope by including models that predict for fish tank conditions as well as disease identification from images in addition to the mentioned applications. Utilizing cutting-edge methods for visual analysis and machine learning is part of the extension. The model will examine several variables, including water quality, temperature, as well as habitat conditions for fish tanks in order to offer insights into the ideal environment for various fish species. Furthermore, by using cutting-edge image processing algorithms to find symptoms of diseases in fish based on imagery, the study will delve into the prediction of fish disease. This thorough approach improves the methodology's adaptability while also addressing important aspects of fishkeeping, which helps to manage aquatic environments more holistically.

V. BUILD MODEL

A. Importing Libraries

```
from transformers import AutoModelForQuestionAnswering, AutoTokenizer, pipeline
import torch.nn.functional as F
from torch import Tensor
from transformers import AutoTokenizer, AutoModel
import os

import torch
from torchvision import datasets, models
from torchvision import transforms as T
from torch.nn import functional as F
from PIL import Image
import cv2
import albumentations as A

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from pycocotools.coco import COCO
from albumentations.pytorch import ToTensorV2
from torchvision.utils import draw_bounding_boxes
import torchvision.transforms as transforms
```

1. 1) Transformers

Hugging Face's Transformers is a potent NLP library that provides tools and APIs for downloading and training cutting-edge pretrained models. Users have flexibility in their choice of framework thanks to its support for seamless integration with well-known deep learning libraries like Jax, PyTorch, and TensorFlow. Modern natural language processing for PyTorch and TensorFlow 2.0 is offered by the library, formerly known as pytorch-transformers. Hugging Face and the community maintain it, and it provides machine learning models for PyTorch, TensorFlow, and JAX.

2. 2) Torch

"Torch" is frequently used to refer to the PyTorch library, an open-source machine learning framework that makes it easier to prototype research and deploy it in real-world settings. PyTorch offers a deep learning-optimized tensor library with support for both GPUs and CPUs.

3. 3) PyTorch

The PyTorch project's Torchvision component is crucial because it offers a library with well-known datasets, model architectures, and typical image transformations for computer vision tasks. The scope of PyTorch's computer vision capabilities is increased by this.

4) cv2

The Python bindings for the OpenCV (Open Source Computer Vision) library are referred to as cv2. Various features and tools for video and image processing, computer vision tasks, and machine learning applications are provided by the robust open-source library known as OpenCV.

5) Tensor

The idea of vectors and matrices is generalized in mathematics by the concept of tensors. Tensors are multidimensional arrays used in machine learning and deep learning that can represent data of various levels of complexity. Tensors can be zero-dimensional scalars, one-dimensional vectors, two-dimensional matrices, or have higher dimensions.

6) Albumentations

A Python library called Albumentations was created for quick and adaptable image augmentations. It is a useful tool for computer vision, deep learning, and machine learning tasks because it effectively implements a wide range of image transformation operations. To improve the caliber of training data, the library is well known for its effectiveness and is frequently used in business, deep learning research, and machine learning competitions.

B) Training the model

Fish Recognition from Images

```
def train_one_epoch(model, optimizer, loader, device, epoch):
    model.to(device)
    model.train()

    all_losses = []
    all_losses_dict = {}

    for images, targets in tqdm(loader):
        images = list(image.to(device) for image in images)
        targets = [(k, torch.tensor(v).to(device) for k, v in t.items()) for t in targets]

        loss_dict = model(images, targets)
        losses = sum(loss for loss in loss_dict.values())
        loss_dict_append = (k, v.item() for k, v in loss_dict.items())
        loss_value = losses.item()

        all_losses.append(loss_value)
        all_losses_dict.append(loss_dict_append)

    if not math.isfinite(loss_value):
        print("Loss is {} (loss_value), stopping training".format(loss_value))
        print(loss_dict)
        sys.exit(1)

    optimizer.zero_grad()
    losses.backward()
    optimizer.step()

    all_losses_dict = pd.DataFrame(all_losses_dict)
    print("@epoch {}, lr: {:.6f}, loss: {:.6f}, loss_classifier: {:.6f}, loss_box: {:.6f}, loss_rm_box: {:.6f}, loss_object: {:.6f}".format(
        epoch, optimizer.param_groups[0]['lr'], np.mean(all_losses),
        all_losses_dict['loss_classifier'].mean(),
        all_losses_dict['loss_box_rm'].mean(),
        all_losses_dict['loss_rm_box_rm'].mean(),
        all_losses_dict['loss_objectness'].mean()
    ))
```

```
num_epochs=10  
  
for epoch in range(num_epochs):  
    train_one_epoch(model, optimizer, train_loader, device, epoch)
```

C) Results

About the fish:

similar fishes

Ask Question

Similar Fish Species:

- Black Arowana
- Arowana
- Blue Arowana
- African Lungfish

About the fish:

ph level of the fish

Ask Question

Solution :

6.5 to 7.5

About the fish:

Identify the fishes

Ask Question

Identified fishes :

shark,fish

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, a strong framework for addressing various applications is presented by the incorporation of a cutting-edge algorithm for calculating sentence similarity and a thorough analysis and classification methodology. In order to provide an advanced knowledge of question semantics, the research skillfully straddles the worlds of natural language processing, image processing, and similarity metrics. The applications range from fish recognition through faster R-CNN models via MobileNetV3-Large to fish similarity evaluation using k-NN with cosine similarity. Context-based question answering using the RoBERTa-base model using the SQuAD 2.0 dataset is also included. Particularly in the area of fish-related queries, this adaptable approach not only promotes image-based recognition as well as similarity evaluation but also improves contextual inquiry.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] For Improving Sentence Representation, Token Attention Sentence-BERT by JAEJIN SEO, SANGWON LEE, LING_LIU AND WONIK CHOI - In this study, TA-SBERT 2020
- [2] Sentence Similarity Based on Contexts by Xiaofei Sun, Yuxian Meng, Xiang Ao, Fei Wu, Tianwei Zhang, Jiwei Li, and Chun Fan
- [3] Hyun-Je Song, Su-Hwan Yoon, Seong-Bae Park Question Difficulty Estimation Based on Attention Model for Question Answering 17 December 2021
- [4] N. Reimers and I. Gurevych, "Sentence-BERT: Sentence embeddings using Siamese BERT-networks," in Proc. Conf. Empirical Methods Natural Lang. Process. 9th Int. Joint Conf. Natural Lang. Process. (EMNLP/ICNLP), 2019,

[5] Nils Reimers and Iryna Gurevych. 2019. Sentence-bert: Sentence embeddings using Siamese BERT-networks. arXiv preprint arXiv:1908.10084

[6] Zhiguo Wang, Haitao Mi, and Abraham Ittycheriah. 2016. Sentence similarity learning by lexical decomposition and composition. In Proceedings of COLING 2016, the 26th International Conference on Computational Linguistics